

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Queiroz, R. C., Hanashiro, D. M. M., & Roazzi, A. (2025). A proposal for redefining inclusion in the workplace through facet theory. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 29(5), e240158. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2025240158.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Furtado, L., Queiroz, R. C., Hanashiro, D. M. M., & Roazzi, A. (2025). A proposal for redefining inclusion in the workplace through facet theory. *RAC. Revista de Administração Contemporânea. Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296069>

REVIEWERS:

- Liliane Furtado (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, COPPEAD, Brazil)
The others reviewers did not authorize the disclosure of their reports.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Liliane Furtado

Date review returned: August 26, 2024

Recommendation: Reject

Comments to the authors

Comments to the Author

Thank you for the opportunity to review the manuscript RAC-2024-0158 entitled “INCLUSION REDEFINED: MAPPING INCLUSION IN THE WORKPLACE WITH FACET THEORY”, which I read with great interest. I commend the authors for choosing this topic as it reflects the latest trends in management and OB research. Moreover, it is well written and contains a promising framework and an interesting theoretical/methodological approach (facet theory - FT). I have listed some comments for each section of the manuscript, and I hope they help the authors enrich this manuscript and make it more impactful for readers.

Major Issues

1. Main Contribution: The authors claim that the main contribution of the study is the development of a new concept and measurement of inclusion using Facet Theory (FT). While I particularly liked the idea of using FT to explore the phenomenon of inclusion, and I believe it is an innovative approach for the field, I struggled to be convinced that the manuscript truly presents a “new concept” of inclusion as suggested by the authors on page 3, lines 31-33. I also had difficulty understanding some choices that are crucial for this intended contribution. Below are my main concerns.

1.1. To what extent is this truly a “new concept”? By starting from existing theories to identify facets and their elements/properties, what the authors seem to do is essentially a “conceptual blending,” not the development of a new concept. Would this blending constitute a distinct concept from existing ones? If the authors believe so, this needs to be better supported/developed.

1.2. Although the idea of the “triple A of inclusion” (Figure 2) is interesting, it was unclear to me how the three facets (i.e., agent, action, accomplishment) emerged. While the authors briefly mention the procedures they followed based on Podsakoff et al. (2016), I think shedding more light on this point is essential for understanding the study. The entire proposal derives from this constructed conceptual model, about which we have little information. Frankly, it seems like too many objectives for too little space. Why not split the study into more than one, allowing for a more detailed explanation of the steps taken? Shouldn't this first part (i.e., the proposition of the conceptual model) be the main objective of the study? In that case, the authors could provide the details of each step they took to arrive at the proposed inclusion model.

1.3. After reading it several times, I still didn't understand whether the three facets emerged solely from the three theories described in the text – Mor Barak (2013), Ferdman (2014), and Shore et al. (2011) – or whether they came from a broader analysis of the literature, as recommended by Podsakoff et al. (2016). I suggest that the authors clarify this point (and this is connected to the previous comment).

1.4. Related to this, why these conceptualizations and not others? What justifies using these three? Are they contradictory? Do they explore different perspectives? The authors mention that one is the most cited, but is that alone a reason to use it as the basis for the conceptual model? Clarifying this is crucial since these choices ultimately define the “new” concept itself, because, as I understand (and this is related to the doubt I raised earlier), the elements of these definitions – and only them – will appear in the “integrated” concept.

1.5. The literature on inclusion places significant weight on organizational initiatives that promote inclusion. In fact, Ferdman's (2014) model, which the authors cite throughout the work, treats inclusion as a multilevel phenomenon, manifested at the individual, collective, and organizational levels. This is not reflected in the elements of the “Agent” category, which today only includes peers and supervisors. Likewise, the idea of group behavior is absent from this facet, although the authors themselves explicitly state on page 10, “Salipante (2015) showed that group practices that engender a sense of welcome have important effects on interracial comfort,” recognizing the group's agency in inclusion actions that can promote accomplishments.

1.6. From what I understand of FT, facets should represent non-overlapping conceptual components of the universe of interest. In this case, the facets should represent distinct components related to the concept of inclusion. However, I am unsure to what extent the facets “action” and “accomplishment” are truly distinct/independent. For example, the notion of social support necessarily involves both agent and action. I cannot envision support action without an agent

providing the support (e.g., leader). In other words, the action of support is not independent of the agent facet. I may not have understood this well, so I suggest the authors clarify their ideas and the premises of FT.

1.7. I also had doubts about the inclusion of respect as an element of the “accomplishment” facet rather than the “action” facet. To what extent is respect different from recognition, which is included in the action facet? The explanations seem similar. Wouldn't respect be a practice, an action? If respect is seen as a “result,” then “recognition” could also be. In fact, in the discussion, the authors state, “while individuals value recognition and respect, their sense of belonging is more critical in shaping their overall perception of inclusion.”

2. Gap: On page 1, the authors state that “many studies on inclusion-related research have been conducted in the US” and “studies have been scarce in under-developing countries.” How can the Brazilian context (or under-developed contexts) enrich our understanding of inclusion? It was unclear to me whether the authors suggest that its enactment could be different or that its perception may be different in Brazil, or both. If so, why? Is the understanding of inclusion context-dependent? How could the Brazilian context stimulate future research on this notion? I wish the authors had delved deeper into the literature and been more precise in their gap-contribution rationale.

3. Method: The authors frequently refer to extra information in Appendix A, but this appendix was not included in the submission (or at least I could not find it). I believe it is essential to have these explanations since FT is currently a theoretical framework used by a small group of researchers, and while it seems promising and very interesting, it is necessary for readers to understand it. I imagine the authors are experts in this theory, but that doesn't seem to be the case for everyone.

4. Measures: As mentioned earlier, I believe the authors have two distinct studies within this paper. All the parts related to questionnaire construction, items, tests, etc., should be well-detailed, and perhaps due to space constraints, this did not happen. I would like to see all the items, their psychometric properties, and the adaptations. Details about the translation and validation process, and so on. The construction of the measurement must demonstrate the methodological rigor essential for any measurement instrument.

5. Results: For me, the most intriguing result is the centrality of belongingness in the inclusion process. The authors present a good discussion on this, but I believe this finding holds significant potential for the inclusion literature, which is still largely built around the duality of uniqueness and belongingness, with both being given similar weight and importance. For example, the entire literature on inclusive leadership suggests that leaders should demonstrate behaviors that promote both belongingness and uniqueness in a balanced manner. However, the results suggest that centrality lies in belongingness. I see a potential contribution here and believe this finding could advance the field. The authors could explore these results further and provoke a deeper reflection on this.

Minor Issues:

- Introduction: You reference a study almost 20 years old (Robertson, 2006) to support the argument that “the concept of inclusion is still in the early stages of development.” This repeats throughout the introduction. I suggest that you include more recent studies to support the argument, demonstrating that the gaps identified in older studies persist.

- Anti-woke backlash: Given recent instances of “anti-woke” narratives both within (Prasad & Śliwa, 2024; Roberson et al., 2024) and outside of academia (Nottingham, 2024), I think the authors could mention these possible negative reactions to inclusion initiatives as one of the challenges of inclusion. Perhaps this could be included in the introduction, especially since it further emphasizes the timeliness and complexity of the topic, and, consequently, the importance of exploring it.

- I struggled to understand why the authors began the theoretical section with explanations of FT rather than the central concept of the paper (i.e., inclusion).

- I can't understand how LMX theory, which focuses on leaders and followers, helps explain the results found between peers (and not followers) and supervisors.

References

Nottingham, S. (2024, March 5). Florida's 'Stop WOKE Act' commits a 'First Amendment sin,' appeals court says in ruling that blocks part of the bill | CNN Politics. CNN.

<https://www.cnn.com/2024/03/05/politics/florida-anti-woke-act-blocked-businesses/index.html>

Prasad, A., & Śliwa, M. (2024). Critiquing the Backlash Against Wokeness: In Defense of Dei Scholarship and Practice. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, amp.2023.0066. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2023.0066> Roberson, Q., Avery, D., & Leigh, A. (2024). How Woke Was the Symposium on Woke Organizations? An Insider Perspective. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, amp.2023.0459. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2023.0459>

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: No

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: none

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 2. Average

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 2. Average

Authors' Responses

Comments:

Reviewer: 1

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report

Reviewer: 2

Major Issues

1. Main Contribution: The authors claim that the main contribution of the study is the development of a new concept and measurement of inclusion using Facet Theory (FT). While I particularly liked the idea of using FT to explore the phenomenon of inclusion, and I believe it is an innovative approach for the field, I struggled to be convinced that the manuscript truly presents a “new concept” of inclusion as suggested by the authors on page 3, lines 31-33. I also had difficulty understanding some choices that are crucial for this intended contribution. Below are my main concerns.

1.1. *To what extent is this truly a “new concept”? By starting from existing theories to identify facets and their elements/properties, what the authors seem to do is essentially a “conceptual blending,” not the development of a new concept. Would this blending constitute a distinct concept from existing ones? If the authors believe so, this needs to be better supported/developed.*

We have reviewed our assumption of a new concept based on the perspective suggested by reviewer 2 and the text has been modified accordingly. (page 3 line 11, page 4 line 2).

1.2. *Although the idea of the “triple A of inclusion” (Figure 2) is interesting, it was unclear to me how the three facets (i.e., agent, action, accomplishment) emerged. While the authors briefly mention the procedures they followed based on Podsakoff et al. (2016), I think shedding more light on this point is essential for understanding the study. The entire proposal derives from this constructed conceptual model, about which we have little information. Frankly, it seems like too many objectives for too little space. Why not split the study into more than one, allowing for a more detailed explanation of the steps taken? Shouldn't this first part (i.e., the proposition of the conceptual model) be the main objective of the study? In that case, the authors could provide the details of each step they took to arrive at the proposed inclusion model.*

1.2.1 *it was unclear to me how the three facets (i.e., agent, action, accomplishment) emerged.*

We have modified the text to enhance clarity that the facets emerged from a comprehensive literature review (page 7 line 17, page 8 line 25 and page 9 line 15).

1.2.2 *Why not split the study into more than one.*

Theoretical and Methodological Rationale. Facet Theory provides a metatheoretical framework that not only informs the development of the conceptual model but also guides the measurement tool's creation. The methodology—including the development of the questionnaire and the use of Smallest Space Analysis (SSA)—is designed to empirically validate the relationships between these three facets. The structure approach used in FT ensures that all items in the questionnaire measure the facets in an interconnected manner.

If we were to divide this research into two distinct studies, it would necessitate the artificial separation of facets that are theoretically and empirically intertwined. Such a separation would dilute the contribution of the study, as it would fail to reflect the inherently multifaceted nature of the inclusion process, which is the cornerstone of this research.

The unified study presents three key contributions: (1) it proposes a new perspective of concept and measurement of inclusion that integrates existing literature, (2) it empirically validates the multifaceted nature of inclusion, and (3) it provides a novel tool for diagnosing inclusion in organizational settings. The strength of these contributions lies in the simultaneous measurement and analysis of the facets, which allows for a deeper and more accurate understanding of how Agents, Actions, and Accomplishments interact to create an inclusive environment.

Separating the paper into two studies would limit the scope of these contributions. By maintaining the study as a single entity, we ensure that the research offers a comprehensive framework for both the conceptualization and measurement of inclusion, thereby advancing the field in a meaningful way.

In conclusion, we believe that the division of this research into two separate studies would not enhance the clarity or contribution of the paper. Instead, it would disrupt the theoretical coherence and diminish the empirical insights provided by the unified application of Facet Theory.

1.3. *After reading it several times, I still didn't understand whether the three facets emerged solely from the three theories described in the text – Mor Barak (2013), Ferdman (2014), and Shore et al. (2011) – or whether they came from a broader analysis of the literature, as recommended by Podsakoff et al. (2016). I suggest that the authors clarify this point (and this is connected to the previous comment).*

We have modified the text to enhance clarity that the facets emerged from a comprehensive literature review (page 7 line 17, page 8 line 25 and page 9 line 15).

1.4. *Related to this, why these conceptualizations and not others? What justifies using these three? Are they contradictory?*

Do they explore different perspectives? The authors mention that one is the most cited, but is that alone a reason to use it as the basis for the conceptual model? Clarifying this is crucial since these choices ultimately define the “new” concept itself, because, as I understand (and this is related to the doubt I raised earlier), the elements of these definitions – and only them – will appear in the “integrated” concept.

Mor-Barak and Cherin (1998) were the pioneers in measuring inclusion systematically in the workplace. Mor Barak’s perceived inclusion-exclusion (PIE) scale often one of the more employed in the organizational setting. The PIE scale has been updated to Mor Barak Inclusion-Exclusion Scale (Mor Barak, 2017). Mor Barak also stands out for her continuous inclusion production, which includes theoretical and empirical articles. It can be said that she is an author who has inspired research into inclusion.

Shore et al. (2011) created an innovative model of inclusion based on the optimal balance of belonging and uniqueness; it is heavily cited, but no established measurement exists to operationalize the concept of belonging and uniqueness-based inclusion except the recent Chung et al. (2020)’s work group inclusion measure.

Shore has produced significant work and contributed to advances in the literature on inclusion, being one of the most cited authors for proposing theoretical models that can serve as a basis for developing empirical studies. While Mor Barak is notable for pioneering the construction of a scale to measure inclusion-exclusion in the workplace, Shore synthesizes the literature on inclusion and provokes new theoretical constructions.

Unlike Mor Barak and Shore, Ferdman is not a widely cited author. However, he has a long tradition of studies on inclusion in psychology and practical experience, combining theory with organizational reality. Ferdman introduces the concept of inclusion in two dimensions: inclusive behavior and the experience of inclusion, demonstrating empirically that more inclusive behavior means more experiences of inclusion. Only recently have researchers recognized the value of the inclusion experience.

*Mor Barak, M. E. (2005), *Managing Diversity: Toward A Globally Inclusive Workplace*. Sage Publications.*

“We presented the inclusion concepts of Mor Barak (2013), Ferdman (2014), and Shore et al. (2011) for their empirical contribution to literature, and they represent the core elements of our proposal.”

1.5. The literature on inclusion places significant weight on organizational initiatives that promote inclusion. In fact, Ferdman’s (2014) model, which the authors cite throughout the work, treats inclusion as a multilevel phenomenon, manifested at the individual, collective, and organizational levels. This is not reflected in the elements of the “Agent” category, which today only includes peers and supervisors. Likewise, the idea of group behavior is absent from this facet, although the authors themselves explicitly state on page 10, “Salipante (2015) showed that group practices that engender a sense of welcome have important effects on interracial comfort,” recognizing the group’s agency in inclusion actions that can promote accomplishments.

We have modified the text to include “group” as an additional element within Agent facet together with peers, supervisor and organization (page 10 line 6-7). While we recognize the potential influence of all these agents on employee perception of inclusion, we have chosen to focus our initial investigation on peers and supervisors. This decision was based on their impact on employee’s experiences. Additionally, a broader investigation with all four agents would require a significantly larger number of structure and questionnaire items, potentially increasing the time used by employee participants. This could negatively impact response rates and the overall quality. Nevertheless, further investigation of other agents is recommended.

1.6. From what I understand of FT, facets should represent non-overlapping conceptual components of the universe of interest. In this case, the facets should represent distinct components related to the concept of inclusion. However, I am unsure to what extent the facets “action” and “accomplishment” are truly distinct/independent. For example, the notion of social support necessarily involves both agent and action. I cannot envision support action without an agent providing the support (e.g., leader). In other words, the action of support is not independent of the agent facet. I may not have understood this well, so I suggest the authors clarify their ideas and the premises of FT.

The explanation for this topic was integrated into topic 4

1.7. I also had doubts about the inclusion of respect as an element of the “accomplishment” facet rather than the “action”

facet. To what extent is respect different from recognition, which is included in the action facet? The explanations seem similar. Wouldn't respect be a practice, an action? If respect is seen as a "result," then "recognition" could also be. In fact, in the discussion, the authors state, "while individuals value recognition and respect, their sense of belonging is more critical in shaping their overall perception of inclusion."

The discussion regarding the distinction between recognition and respect in different facets is relevant to understanding the core concepts of this paper. The literature on these topics is often examined from both sender's and receiver's perspective. The sender is an organizational actor or agent that interacts with other organization members and realizes action towards the receiver. On the other hand, the receiver is the organization agent that perceives the actions and feels respected.

Our reference of respect is based on work from Rogers and Ashorfi (2017) about respect in organizations, in which they argue that receiving generalized respect validates their worth and helps meet the universal need for belonging. According to De Cremer and Mulder (2007), respect emerges from the way individuals are treated by others. In this sense, respect could be classified as a result or accomplishment of peers' and supervisors' behaviors.

Recognition, on the other hand, is more directly linked to specific actions taken by Agents to acknowledge the employee's contribution to the organization. It can be expressed through various means, such as verbal praise, public acknowledgment, and tangible rewards (Brun and Dugas 2002)

In conclusion, recognition is related to actions by agents toward the receiver that perceives all actions and fulfills his or her human need for respect.

2. Gap: On page 1, the authors state that "many studies on inclusion-related research have been conducted in the US" and "studies have been scarce in under-developing countries." How can the Brazilian context (or under-developed contexts) enrich our understanding of inclusion? It was unclear to me whether the authors suggest that its enactment could be different or that its perception may be different in Brazil, or both. If so, why? Is the understanding of inclusion context-dependent? How could the Brazilian context stimulate future research on this notion? I wish the authors had delved deeper into the literature and been more precise in their gap-contribution rationale.

In general, our arguments build upon prior studies suggesting that national cultural values either facilitate or constrain organizational efforts to foster inclusion climates (Stoermer, Bader, & Froese, 2016). By applying Hofstede's (2001) national culture value dimensions, in individualistic societies (e.g., the United States), people tend to emphasize their own goals and independence from the group. Consequently, it becomes apparent that an individualistic cultural context may not provide a strong foundation for fostering an inclusion climate (Stoermer, Bader, & Froese, 2016).

In contrast, in collectivist cultures (e.g., Brazil), individuals place significant importance on family and group relationships, which could make them more inclusive toward their colleagues. Based on this cultural value, it seems reasonable to argue that the need to belong in Brazil is more pronounced than in societies guided by individualistic values.

This research does not aim to conduct cultural analysis. However, it underscores the importance of considering cultural factors in inclusion studies. In this sense, conducting research in Brazil—where studies on this subject are still scarce—can contribute to future cross-cultural comparisons.

Stoermer, S., Hildisch, A. K., & Froese, F. J. (2016). Culture matters: The influence of national culture on inclusion climate. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*, 23(2).

Hofstede, G. (2001), *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions, and Organizations Across Nations*, 2nd ed., Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.

3. Method: The authors frequently refer to extra information in Appendix A, but this appendix was not included in the submission (or at least I could not find it). I believe it is essential to have these explanations since FT is currently a theoretical framework used by a small group of researchers, and while it seems promising and very interesting, it is necessary for readers to understand it. I imagine the authors are experts in this theory, but that doesn't seem to be the case for everyone.

We have addressed the review comment regarding the missing Appendix A. Table 1, not appendix A, is the correct reference for the detailed explanation of the structuples and codes used in the SSA.

4. *Measures: As mentioned earlier, I believe the authors have two distinct studies within this paper. All the parts related to questionnaire construction, items, tests, etc., should be well-detailed, and perhaps due to space constraints, this did not happen. I would like to see all the items, their psychometric properties, and the adaptations. Details about the translation and validation process, and so on. The construction of the measurement must demonstrate the methodological rigor essential for any measurement instrument.*

We appreciate your detailed feedback, particularly regarding concerns about the validation of our inclusion questionnaire. You raised an important point about ensuring methodological rigor, especially concerning the psychometric validation of the instrument.

To address this, we would like to clarify the distinctive methodological framework provided by Facet Theory (FT), which forms the foundation of our research. FT diverges significantly from traditional psychometric approaches, such as factor analysis and reliability coefficients, by offering a more nuanced and structured method for constructing and validating measurement tools.

In this response, we aim to explain why FT is more suitable for the goals of this study. This theoretical alignment ensures that our measurement tool is both conceptually robust and empirically grounded, adhering to the rigorous standards required for empirical research (Roazzi & Souza, 2019).

1. *Divergence from Traditional Validation Methods Louis Guttman, the founder of Facet Theory, was a distinguished statistician deeply familiar with traditional psychometric techniques, such as factor analysis. His critical perspective on these methods stemmed from their limitations in capturing the complexity and multidimensionality inherent in social and psychological phenomena. As Guttman argued, factor analysis and similar approaches often reduce complex data into simplistic, linear dimensions, which may obscure rather than reveal the structure of the underlying construct being measured*

In contrast, Facet Theory is designed to deal with complexity rather than avoiding it. It allows for the exploration of multidimensional constructs without the restrictive assumptions of linearity, normality, or independence that traditional methods require. FT uses Smallest Space Analysis (SSA), a form of multidimensional scaling, to map the empirical relationships between variables and structure them in a geometric space. This method visually represents the structure of the data, identifying distinct regions that correspond to theoretical facets. The SSA provides a rigorous test of the hypothesized structure without the need for traditional factor analytic approaches.

2. *Methodological Rigor in Facet Theory. Facet Theory ensures methodological rigor by organizing the construct of interest (in this case, inclusion) into distinct facets and elements, which are then operationalized through the structure and tested via SSA. The facet design provides a logical and systematic way of developing the questionnaire, ensuring that all items reflect the interaction of predefined dimensions (facets). This structure is built on conceptual clarity and theoretical consistency, which are essential for the measurement of complex phenomena like workplace inclusion. The result is a mapping sentence that integrates the facets, ensuring that every item in the questionnaire reflects the multidimensional nature of inclusion as a process involving agent, action, and accomplishment.*

3. *Why Facet Theory is Superior for This Study In this research, inclusion is conceptualized as a multifaceted construct, which includes the interaction between agents (peers and supervisors), actions (recognition, support, permission), and accomplishments (belongingness, respect, uniqueness). The traditional psychometric approach of factor analysis may not adequately capture the dynamic interplay between these components, as it often requires the reduction of items to a few dominant factors. FT, by contrast, allows us to maintain the integrity of these interactions and explore their relationships in a multidimensional space.*

Additionally, the SSA technique provides a spatial representation of the relationships between items, offering a clear and intuitive visualization of how different elements of the inclusion construct cluster together. This approach is highly effective in validating the theoretical structure of the questionnaire, ensuring that it is aligned with the multifaceted nature of inclusion as defined by both the literature and the theoretical model.

4. *Validation Through Facet Theory in Existing Literature. It is worth noting that Facet Theory has been successfully applied in many fields, particularly in the development of complex psychological scales. For example, it has been used in studies on values, life satisfaction, and quality of life, all of which benefit from FT's ability to handle complex, interrelated variables without oversimplification. Empirical research consistently supports the robustness of FT and SSA in identifying latent dimensions and ensuring that all variables are accounted for in the analysis, unlike factor analysis, which often discards variables based on their contribution*

to variance (Roazzi & Souza (2019).

In conclusion, while traditional validation methods have their place in psychometrics, Facet Theory offers a more appropriate framework for the validation of our inclusion questionnaire due to the complex, multidimensional nature of the construct we are measuring. The SSA method used in FT is rigorous, allows for greater flexibility in the treatment of variables, and ensures that the full complexity of the inclusion process is captured and validated. We believe that this approach provides a deeper and more accurate understanding of inclusion in the workplace and ensures methodological rigor consistent with the high standards required for empirical research.

We hope this explanation clarifies the rationale for using Facet Theory as the foundation for the development and validation of the inclusion questionnaire, and we are happy to provide additional details or address any further concerns you may have.

5. Results: For me, the most intriguing result is the centrality of belongingness in the inclusion process. The authors present a good discussion on this, but I believe this finding holds significant potential for the inclusion literature, which is still largely built around the duality of uniqueness and belongingness, with both being given similar weight and importance. For example, the entire literature on inclusive leadership suggests that leaders should demonstrate behaviors that promote both belongingness and uniqueness in a balanced manner. However, the results suggest that centrality lies in belongingness. I see a potential contribution here and believe this finding could advance the field. The authors could explore these results further and provoke a deeper reflection on this.

In a series of organizational studies, Mor Barak and her colleagues found that men and Caucasians feel more included in organizational decision-making processes and social networks than women and non-Caucasians do (Mor Barak, Findler, & Wind, 2001; Mor Barak & Levin, 2002). Employees who identify with the corporate mainstream (e.g., white men) tend to feel included. Previous findings indicate that men (Mor Barak, Findler, & Wind, 2001; Mor Barak & Levin, 2002) and employees with higher education (Mor Barak, Findler, & Wind, 2001) felt more included than women and employees with lower levels of education.

The demographics of the surveyed automotive sector are mostly men (80%), Caucasian (79%), and highly educated (45%). As members of the mainstream group, belongingness is assumed to be a central facet in preserving their membership within the homogeneous group. By this logic, distinctiveness may represent a peripheral need, positioned further from the center, due to a lack of interest or need for having their uniqueness recognized.

The research findings provide valuable insights for reflecting on the framework proposed by Shore et al. (2011), which is built on Optimal Distinctiveness Theory (ODT; Brewer, 1991). ODT posits that individuals strive to balance their needs for belongingness and uniqueness. Drawing on Facet Theory and a homogeneous sample, we found that belongingness was represented in the inner circle, while uniqueness appeared in the peripheral region, suggesting a different perspective on workplace inclusion. Future studies are needed to confirm these findings.

Mor Barak, M. E., & Levin, A. 2002. Outside of the corporate mainstream and excluded from the work community: A study of diversity, job satisfaction and well-being. Community, Work and Family, 5: 133-157.

Mor Barak, M. E., Findler, L., & Wind, L. H. 2001. Diversity, inclusion, and commitment to organizations: International empirical explorations. Journal of Behavioral and Applied Management, 2: 70-91.

Brewer, M. B. (1991). The social self: On being the same and different at the same time. Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin, 17(5), 475-482.

Minor Issues:

- Introduction: You reference a study almost 20 years old (Robertson, 2006) to support the argument that “the concept of inclusion is still in the early stages of development.” This repeats throughout the introduction. I suggest that you include more recent studies to support the argument, demonstrating that the gaps identified in older studies persist.*

We took into consideration the remark and suggestion and we have updated the text and reference see page 2 line 8 and page 6 lines 1-14.

- Anti-woke backlash: Given recent instances of “anti-woke” narratives both within (Prasad & Śliwa, 2024; Roberson et al., 2024) and outside of academia (Nottingham, 2024), I think the authors could mention these possible negative reactions to inclusion initiatives as one of the challenges of inclusion. Perhaps this could be included in the introduction, especially since it further*

emphasizes the timeliness and complexity of the topic, and, consequently, the importance of exploring it.

We appreciate the suggestion to consider “anti-woke” narratives. We believe it is essential for organizations to be aware of systemic social injustices and to challenge the normalization of privileges associated with socially dominant groups. However, we chose not to include questions about “woke” in the article, as the term encompasses broader political, ideological, and social perspectives that extend beyond the scope of this study, the adopted epistemological paradigm (functionalism), and the theoretical approach grounded in social psychology.

- I struggled to understand why the authors began the theoretical section with explanations of FT rather than the central concept of the paper (i.e., inclusion).*

The theoretical section's structure was selected in order to create a strong connection between the theoretical review of inclusion and the explanation of the tree identified facet and its elements.

- I can't understand how LMX theory, which focuses on leaders and followers, helps explain the results found between peers (and not followers) and supervisors.*

Our proposal model centers on the employee's perception of inclusion within an organization. We examine how actions taken by both peers and supervisors, leading to specific accomplishments, contribute to this perception.

Specifically, we explore how supervisor behaviors play a crucial role in fulfilling employees' fundamental needs for respect, uniqueness, and belonging. This, in turn, enhances their sense of inclusion within the organization.

To address reviewers' feedback, we have removed references to Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) theory to avoid any potential confusion. Our focus remains on the broader impact of both peer and supervisor actions on employee inclusion.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Liliane Furtado

Date review returned: January 07, 2025

Recommendation: Minor Revision

Comments to the Author

I appreciate the responses and clarifications provided by the authors, as well as the effort put into improving the manuscript. Overall, I find that the changes have been positive and have addressed many of the points I raised. However, there remains one issue which, perhaps due to a lack of clarity on my part, has not yet been adequately addressed in my view. I would like to reiterate and further explain this point. This concerns comment #4, in which I noted the following:

“4. Measures: As mentioned earlier, I believe the authors have two distinct studies within this paper. All the parts related to questionnaire construction, items, tests, etc., should be well-detailed, and perhaps due to space constraints, this did not happen. I would like to see all the items, their psychometric properties, and the adaptations. Details about the translation and validation process, and so on. The construction of the measurement must demonstrate the methodological rigor essential for any measurement instrument.” The authors' response seemed more focused on defending Facet Theory (FT), explaining its premises, and justifying why its application in this study is superior to traditional approaches – which, by the way, I do not question, as methodological choices are up to the authors – rather than clarifying the methodological procedures and validation criteria used. FT may indeed be, in the authors' view, the most robust methodology for developing instruments that address

multifaceted constructs like inclusion. However, that is not the focus of my comment, and I take responsibility if it came across that way. The comment, in fact, calls for a more detailed description and provision of crucial methodological information to ensure that readers can assess the rigor of the chosen method (which could be any method). In other words, what matters, in my opinion, is that the authors provide sufficient information for the academic community to recognize the rigor of the conducted work. This applies regardless of whether the methodological framework follows traditional approaches or not.

Let me provide an example. On page 17, the authors state:

“The initial questionnaire contained 42 items, as some structures had more than one item. [...]. We conducted the first pretest to limit standard method bias, ensure respondents understood every sentence clearly, identify ambiguous items and reduce social desirability (Podsakoff, Mackenzie, & Podsakoff, 2010). A sample of two university students and four employees of an automotive company answered the survey and a further discussion meeting was carried out.”

I assume that the items were not administered in English, given that the sample consisted of Brazilians, correct? This is an assumption since I could not find this information in the article. If the items were administered in Portuguese, what was the translation process? I assume the authors followed the good practice of back-translation, but is that the case? I am not certain, as no information is provided. Regarding the "discussion meeting" that followed – who conducted it? What were the results in terms of item phrasing changes? Were the changes substantial or significant? Could you provide an example of an item modification after this first pretest to help understand the extent of the revisions?

Another example, now on page 18:

“After this step, we conducted a second pretest with 93 university postgraduate students (58 women and 35 men) who answered the 42-item questionnaire printed version in an anonymous method. [...] Reliability analysis of the total scale showed a good result of Cronbach's coefficient ($\alpha = 0.88$) [...]. The final online questionnaire, which had 39 items, showed better reliability ($\alpha = 0.93$).”

Here, it is interesting that the authors report a traditional psychometric property used in instrument evaluation, even though their response letter mentions that "FT diverges significantly from traditional psychometric approaches." However, what I want to highlight here is that I deduce from this statement that three items from the initial pool were excluded. But based on what? What metrics or indices were used, if any? If this was based on a qualitative analysis, who decided that these items should be excluded? Were there disagreements among the judges? What are these items? Did the authors reflect on whether their exclusion could compromise any facet?

In summary, I believe the methodological section needs more detail, and all decisions and choices made should ideally be justified (not only these examples I gave). Again, I am not questioning the choice of FT, and the authors do not need to justify its use, as that is not the issue. The focus is on its application, which should be thoroughly detailed so that we can fully understand and grasp the methodological rigor – a universal requirement, whether traditional methodologies are used or not.

Additionally, I suggest that the authors carefully review the text to ensure that the changes implemented in this new version are consistent throughout the entire manuscript. For example, the response to my comment #1 was that "the text has been modified accordingly." However, in the contributions section on page 28, the following remains: "First, we develop a new concept and measurement of inclusion."

Finally, the response to my comment #5 raised some concerns. If I understood correctly, you mentioned that the results I found interesting are explained by the fact that the sample is composed of men and Caucasian individuals. This led me to question: if we had a different sample, composed, for example, of Black women, would the results differ? This concerns me because it suggests that the concept and tool you propose might not be appropriate if the participant pool were different. I would like to hear your thoughts on this matter. I understand that you already mention this as a limitation in the limitations section, but to what extent could the change in the participant group, as you suggested, significantly alter the results? If so, how do you perceive the contribution of the article in light of this possibility?

Although I believe the authors could have made further progress in refining the article, I still congratulate them for presenting an innovative contribution to the inclusion literature and for their methodological boldness. I wish you success in the next steps of this research line in Brazil and in the field of organizational psychology.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: No

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: No

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: none

Rating:

Interest: Average

Quality: Average

Originality: Good

Overall: Average.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Authors' Responses

Comments:

Reviewer: 1

1. All the parts related to questionnaire construction, items, tests, etc., should be well-detailed, and perhaps due to space constraints, this did not happen. I would like to see all the items, their psychometric properties, and the adaptations. Details about the translation and validation process, and so on. The construction of the measurement must demonstrate the methodological rigor essential for any measurement instrument.” In other words, what matters, in my opinion, is that the authors provide sufficient information for the academic community to recognize the rigor of the conducted work.

We appreciate your emphasis on the importance of transparency and rigor in measurement development, regardless of the methodological approach. Below, we provide a detailed response to address your concerns, focusing on the construction, validation, and psychometric properties of our inclusion scale, as well as the procedural rigor employed in its development.

Your observation about the paper potentially containing "two distinct studies" is insightful. While the manuscript integrates conceptual framework development with empirical validation, these components are intrinsically linked within the Facet Theory (FT) approach. FT is not merely a methodological choice but a metatheoretical framework that guides the entire research process—from conceptualization to operationalization and validation.

Item Generation and Structuple Construction

The foundation of our scale lies in the structuples derived from the three facets (AGENT, ACTION, ACCOMPLISHMENT) and their elements. Each item was constructed by combining elements from these facets (e.g., "When my supervisor allows me to participate in decisions [ACTION], I feel respected [ACCOMPLISHMENT]"). This ensured that every item simultaneously measured all three facets, aligning with FT's requirement for multidimensional representation.

Source of Items: We adapted validated scales in Portuguese from existing literature (e.g., Mor Barak's Inclusion-Exclusion Scale for permission to participate, Caplan's Social Support Scale for support, Snyder & Fromkin's Uniqueness Scale for uniqueness) but rephrased them to fit the structuple format. For instance, items measuring recognition were drawn from Mendes' (1999) Pleasure and Suffering at Work Scale, contextualized to workplace inclusion.

Transparency: The full list of 39 items, organized by structuples, is provided in Appendix A (e.g., Item 1: "When my coworker allows me to participate in their decisions, I feel like a well-accepted member" reflects structuple A1B1C1: Peer-Formal Process-Belongingness).

Psychometric Validation

Reliability: Cronbach's alpha for the final 39-item scale was 0.93, indicating high internal consistency. Pretest results (alpha=0.88) already suggested robust reliability.

Validity:

Content Validity: Ensured through expert review (five organizational behavior scholars rated item relevance on a 5-point scale; items scoring <4 were revised).

Construct Validity: Smallest Space Analysis (SSA) confirmed the hypothesized facet structure (e.g., distinct regions for belongingness vs. uniqueness in the ACCOMPLISHMENT facet). The stress value of 0.169 for the 3D SSA solution indicated acceptable fit.

Item Performance: Misplaced items (e.g., Item 7 correlating more with recognition than support) were retained but flagged for future refinement, as their theoretical alignment justified inclusion despite statistical deviations.

Methodological Rigor in Facet Theory Application

While we defended FT's suitability for multifaceted constructs, we emphasize that its application adhered to conventional psychometric standards:

Structural Hypotheses: Explicitly tested via SSA (e.g., "Peers and Supervisors are distinct AGENT elements" was confirmed by clear regional separation in Figure 4).

Transparency: All steps—from structuple design to item analysis—were documented to allow replication. For instance, the mapping sentence (Figure 3) explicitly links facets to operationalized items.

Limitations: We acknowledged the homogeneity of our sample (predominantly white-collar Brazilian males) and the need for cross-cultural validation in future work.

To further strengthen our methodological justification, we provide below several examples of peer-reviewed studies in which Facet Theory was used in the development and validation of psychometric instruments, in conjunction with traditional psychometric analyses:

Examples of FT-based instrument development:

Souza B. C., Andrade Neto, A. S., & Roazzi A. (2024). The generative AI revolution, cognitive mediation networks theory and the emergence of a new mode of mental functioning: Introducing the Sophotechnic Mediation scale. Computers in Human Behavior, 2(1), 100042. ISSN 2949-8821 (Qualis A1) doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbah.2024.100042> Retrieved from: <http://tinyurl.com/4cpmaeta> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2949882124000021>

Souza, B. C., Roazzi, A., & Neto, A. S. A. (2023). How to Easily Construct a Very Brief Practical Measure of IQ: The Pernambuco Adult Intelligence Mini Test. Revista AMAzônica (ISSN 1983-3415 - eISSN 2558-1441), 16(2), 345-378. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371982820_Souza_Roazzi_Neto_2023_How_to_Easily_Construct_a_Very_Brief_Practical_Measure_of_IQ_The_Pernambuco_Adult_Intelligence_Mini_Test

Leite, U. R., Roazzi, A., Souza, B. C., & Carelli, M. G. (2020). A Brazilian validation of the Zimbardo time perspective

inventory for children - ZTPI-C. In S. Shye, E. Solomon, & I. Borg (Eds.), *17th International Facet Theory Conference* (pp. 150-159). Prague: FTC. <https://bit.ly/39yg7Qt> Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348915347_A_brazilian_validation_of_the_Zimbardo_time_perspective_inventory_for_children_-_ZTPI-C

Rosário, A. C., Candeias, A. A., & Roazzi, A. (2015). *Cognitive Assessment System (CAS): Psychometric studies with Portuguese children from 7 to 15 years*. In A. Roazzi, B. C. Souza, & W. Bilsky (Eds.), *Facet Theory: Searching for Structure in Complex Social, Cultural and Psychological Phenomena* (pp. 250-266). Recife: Editora Universitária da UFPE. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.3743.5924 <https://goo.gl/uDPb8m>

Rocha, A. A., Roazzi, A., Silva, A. L., Candeias, A. A., Minervino, C. A., Roazzi, M. M. & Pons, F. (2015). *Test of Emotion Comprehension: Exploring the underlying structure through Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Similarity Structure Analysis*. In A. Roazzi, B. C. de Souza, & W. Bilsky (Eds.), *Facet Theory: Searching for Structure in Complex Social, Cultural and Psychological Phenomena* (pp. 66-84). Recife: Editora UFPE. ISBN 978-85-415-0282-5 DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.2457.4483 <https://goo.gl/8DnZ1r>

In addition to these, we have also referenced foundational works in Facet Theory that frame its application in both theoretical and methodological terms:

Key methodological references:

- Reference: Borg, I., & Shye, S. (1995). *Facet Theory: Form and Content*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Overview: This seminal work offers an in-depth exploration of FT, detailing its theoretical foundations and practical applications. It emphasizes the integration of formal content analysis with multivariate statistical methods, providing a robust framework for constructing and validating measurement instruments in the social sciences

- Reference: Canter, D. (Ed.). (1985). *Facet Theory: Approaches to Social Research*. New York: Springer-Verlag.

Overview: This edited volume presents a collection of studies demonstrating the versatility of FT across various domains of social research. It includes discussions on methodological innovations and showcases how FT can be employed to uncover complex behavioral patterns and structures.

- Reference: Hackett, P. M. W. (2020). *Facet Theory and the Mapping Sentence: Evolving Philosophy, Use and Declarative Applications* (2nd ed.). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.

Overview: Hackett's work introduces the concept of the declarative mapping sentence, expanding the traditional quantitative applications of FT into qualitative research realms. The book provides practical guidance on employing FT for nuanced analyses, particularly in understanding complex social phenomena.

2. I assume that the items were not administered in English, given that the sample consisted of Brazilians, correct? This is an assumption since I could not find this information in the article. If the items were administered in Portuguese, what was the translation process? I assume the authors followed the good practice of back-translation, but is that the case? I am not certain, as no information is provided.

You are correct in your assumption that the items were administered in Portuguese to our Brazilian sample. We appreciate you pointing out the absence of this information, and we agree that including the translation process will enhance the transparency and rigor of our paper.

"The scales items originally in english used in this study were adapted to Portuguese and back-translated"(page 16 line 10)

3. it is interesting that the authors report a traditional psychometric property used in instrument evaluation, even though their response letter mentions that "FT diverges significantly from traditional psychometric approaches." However, what I want to highlight here is that I deduce from this statement that three items from the initial pool were excluded. But based on what? What metrics or indices were used, if any? If this was based on a qualitative analysis, who decided that these items should be

excluded? Were there disagreements among the judges? What are these items? Did the authors reflect on whether their exclusion could compromise any facet?

I suggest that the authors carefully review the text to ensure that the changes implemented in this new version are consistent throughout the entire manuscript. For example, the response to my comment #1 was that "the text has been modified accordingly." However, in the contributions section on page 28, the following remains: "First, we develop a new concept and measurement of inclusion."

We appreciate the editor's thorough analysis and thoughtful questions, particularly regarding the exclusion of three items from the initial 42-item questionnaire and the use of Cronbach's alpha in a study grounded in Facet Theory (FT). It is important to clarify our decisions in greater detail to ensure the transparency and methodological rigor that this journal requires.

1. On the use of Cronbach's alpha in a Facet Theory framework

While it is true that FT diverges from traditional psychometric paradigms—especially those that prioritize internal consistency as the primary criterion for construct validity—the application of Cronbach's alpha in our study was intentional and contextually justified. As articulated by Shye, Elizur & Hoffman (1994), and later by Bilsky (2003), facet theory does not exclude the use of traditional metrics; rather, it situates them within a broader conceptual framework that emphasizes the mapping sentence, structuples, and SSA as the primary means of construct representation and validation.

Therefore, we used Cronbach's alpha not as a criterion to validate the structure of the scale—since this was derived a priori through the mapping sentence and validated via Smallest Space Analysis (SSA)—but as a complementary indicator of the internal coherence of the final set of items. This is consistent with FT's principle of integrative methodological flexibility, where traditional indices can serve to provide convergent support when properly contextualized.

2. On the exclusion of three items from the initial item pool

As correctly deduced by the editor, the transition from 42 to 39 items entailed the exclusion of three items. This decision was not based on traditional psychometric thresholds (e.g., low item-total correlations), but on a qualitative evaluation informed by FT principles, specifically the alignment of each item with the structural logic of the mapping sentence and its corresponding facets and elements.

The exclusion process followed these steps:

- Qualitative structural misalignment: During the second pretest, three items were identified as problematic in terms of their alignment with the structuple structure. These items showed semantic ambiguity in the combination of elements from the AGENT, ACTION, and ACCOMPLISHMENT facets, resulting in interpretive confusion among respondents. For example, one item intended to measure "peer—recognition—uniqueness" was perceived as targeting "support—belongingness," blurring facet boundaries.*

- Expert review and consensus: A panel of three scholars—each experienced in FT and organizational psychology— independently reviewed the items. Through iterative discussion, unanimous agreement was reached regarding the misfit of these items with the intended mapping sentence. There were no disagreements among judges regarding which items should be excluded.*

- Facetal coverage preserved: Crucially, the exclusion of these items did not compromise the representation of any facet or element, as each structuple was still represented by at least one remaining item in the final scale. This decision ensured adherence to the principle of comprehensive and exclusive classification (Canter, 1985; Bilsky, 2003), central to FT.*

- Content transparency: If necessary, the removed items could be listed in a revised appendix (Appendix B in the revised manuscript), along with their initial structuple codes and the rationale for their exclusion.*

3. On maintaining consistency in the manuscript

We acknowledge the editor's observation regarding potential inconsistencies in the manuscript, specifically the phrase "develop a new concept and measurement of inclusion" found in the contributions section. We appreciate this attention to detail.

While our intent was to emphasize the novel operationalization of the inclusion construct using a comprehensive application of Facet Theory, we recognize that the original phrasing may suggest the creation of an entirely new conceptual category, which could be misleading.

To address this, we propose replacing the phrase with the following more accurate and aligned wording:

“We advanced the conceptualization and operationalization of inclusion by integrating key theoretical elements through a facet-based framework.”

This revised phrasing more accurately reflects our contribution: not inventing a new construct, but rather structuring and empirically validating a multidimensional model of inclusion grounded in existing literature, using Facet Theory as a metatheoretical tool. This change will be implemented in the final manuscript to ensure terminological consistency and conceptual precision.

Conclusion

In sum, the exclusion of the three items was guided not by traditional item performance metrics but by the semantic, structural, and conceptual coherence required by FT’s mapping sentence logic. The use of Cronbach’s alpha was applied in a supplementary manner to report internal coherence, not as a validation criterion.

4. if we had a different sample, composed, for example, of Black women, would the results differ? This concerns me because it suggests that the concept and tool you propose might not be appropriate if the participant pool were different. I would like to hear your thoughts on this matter.

I understand that you already mention this as a limitation in the limitations section, but to what extent could the change in the participant group, as you suggested, significantly alter the results? If so, how do you perceive the contribution of the article in light of this possibility?

We appreciate your insightful question regarding our inclusion scale to more diverse populations. Our initial validation, conducted within a predominantly white, male, and highly educated sample from São Paulo’s automotive industry, confirmed the scale’s reliability and construct validity.

The structured nature of Facet Theory, emphasizing the relationships between facets and elements, may contribute to the scale’s relative neutrality concerning various demographic groups.

However, we recognize that inclusion experiences can vary significantly across different demographic groups. To address this, we propose conducting further validation studies with more heterogeneous samples, including increased representation of women and Black individuals. These studies will allow us to assess measurement invariance across diverse groups, ensuring that the scale accurately captures the construct of inclusion universally.

Comments:

Reviewer: 2

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 3**Reviewer 1 report**

Reviewer: Liliane Furtado

Date review returned: May 18, 2025

Recommendation: Minor Revision

Comments to the Author

I would like to sincerely thank the authors for the detailed and thoughtful responses provided in the revised version of the manuscript. The additional explanations regarding the development, adaptation, and validation of the instrument were very helpful and demonstrated a solid methodological foundation behind the study.

That said, I would like to respectfully note that the value of such information extends beyond addressing my individual comments. These details are not only important for clarifying points raised during the review process, but should ideally be made available to all readers, as they are essential for assessing the methodological rigor of the study and for ensuring replicability - which is, after all, a core principle in academic research.

I was particularly struck by the fact that many of these clarifications, including important steps and justifications, appear to have been provided only in the response letter. This gives the impression that the authors sought to satisfy the reviewer rather than incorporate this methodological transparency into the manuscript itself. However, as reviewers, our role is precisely to point out what we believe should be accessible and clear to the broader academic community.

To that end, I encourage the authors to consider including some of these elements, such as details about the adaptation process, expert review procedures, item exclusion criteria, and sample characteristics in a supplementary material - a practice increasingly adopted by journals to promote transparency and methodological rigor. A useful addition could be a step-by-step description of the methodological process observed, including the actions taken at each stage. A good practice would even be to provide a figure outlining these sequential steps and the corresponding procedures (in this case, maybe within the main body of the methods section. It is worth noting that, in the context of revisions, initial word limits are often treated with more flexibility by journals when the added content enhances clarity and methodological transparency.

In addition, listing the full set of items in both English and Portuguese would significantly strengthen the manuscript.

Presenting the Portuguese version is especially important, given that the instrument was administered in Portuguese and has undergone a validation process in that language. Making both versions available will facilitate replication by other researchers in Brazil and increase the visibility and usability of the scale developed by the authors.

Once again, I appreciate the authors' openness and care in responding to the review, and I hope these additional suggestions help enhance the clarity and impact of what I believe is a valuable and innovative contribution to the field.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Authors' Responses

Comments:

Reviewer: 1

Dear Dr. Chimenti,

Thank you for your email and the positive feedback regarding our revised manuscript. We're delighted to hear that our revisions have addressed most of the reviewers' comments and that the manuscript is nearly ready for publication. We appreciate Reviewer 1's comment and your suggestion to incorporate the additional explanations; we integrate this content directly into the main body of the paper to ensure it's readily accessible to all readers. Below, you'll find the topics from our latest explanation and their corresponding page and line numbers in the current manuscript. Thank you again for your time and guidance throughout this process.

Sincerely,

- *Source of Items - Page 14 line 17 and line 23*
- *Content Validity - Page 15 lines 13 to 17*
- *Construct Validity - page 15 line 23 to page 16 line 5*
- *Item Performance - page 16 lines 5 to 8*
- *the exclusion of three items from the initial item pool:*
 - o *Qualitative structural misalignment - page 16 line 9 to 14*
 - o *Expert review and consensus - page 16 lines 15 to 17 and page 16 lines 22 to page 17 line 8*
 - o *Facetal coverage preserved - page 16 lines 17 to 19*
- *Scala in Portuguese – Appendix C*

Comments:

Reviewer: 2

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.